

PREPARATION OF SiC ABSORBENT BY PYROLYZING POLYCARBOSILANE MIXED WITH NANO-Co (Ni) POWDER

Cheng Haifeng, Chen Zhaohui, Li Yongqing, and Zhang Changrui

*Department of Material Engineering and Applied Chemistry,
National University of Defense Technology, Changsha, Hunan, 410073, PRC*

SUMMARY: Modified SiC absorbent was prepared by pyrolyzing polycarbosilane (PCS) mixed with nano-Co(Ni) powder. The pyrolyzation behavior was investigated, and the reaction of nano-Co(Ni) powder with the pyrolyzation product of PCS was proved by TG and IR analysis. The composition of the pyrolyzed and heat-treated product was identified by means of XRD analysis, Co(Ni) silicides were proved to be the primary component that derived from metal powder. The influence of the content of the nano-metal powder in raw mixture and the heat-treatment temperature on the permittivity and permeability of the modified SiC absorbent was studied, and the electromagnetic parameters of the pyrolyzation product could be adjusted in a rather wide range so that it could act as microwave absorbent to fulfill different requirement.

KEYWORDS: nano-Co(Ni) powder, pyrolyzation, PCS, permittivity, permeability

INTRODUCTION

SiC is a kind of semiconductor, and can be used as microwave absorbent. But the conductivity of pure SiC is very low so that it must work together with carbon black or metal powder to achieve better absorbing effect. Another shortcoming of pure SiC is that it is non-magnetic, but it is necessary for microwave absorbent to be magnetic to have low reflectance in broad frequency band with small thickness. There are two ways to improve the electromagnetic property of SiC: purifying and adulteration. We used PCS (polycarbosilane) mixed with nano-Co/Fe powder as precursor to prepare SiC absorbent through a pyrolyzation route. The results showed that the electromagnetic parameters, especially permittivity, could be varied in a rather wide range by altering the content of the nano-Co/Ni and controlling the preparation condition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pyrolyzation of PCS mixed with nano-Co(Ni) powder

The pyrolyzation of PCS mixed with nano-Co(Ni) powder was studied by means of TG (RIGAKU) and IR (HITACHI 270-30) analysis, the results were shown in Fig. 1 and Fig.2. From Fig. 1 we knew that the ceramic yield of PCS mixed with nano-Co(Ni) powder was higher than pure PCS. The reason was that nano-Co(Ni) powder reacted with pyrolyzation product (especially low-molecular-weight gas) and atmosphere (if possible). The weight-loss from 180 to 320 °C was due to the evaporation of residual solvent in PCS, because IR analysis showed no difference between pure PCS and PCS mixed with nano-Co(Ni) below 400°C. We also knew that the content of Si-O-Si bond in the 1000°C pyrolyzation product was reduced as

nano-Ni was added into the precursor. Generally, the pyrolyzing behavior of nano-Ni-mixed PCS was simple to that of pure PCS, except for the reaction of nano-Ni with the pyrolyzation product of PCS.

Fig. 1: TG curve of PCS and PCS mixed with nano-Ni

Note: 1: PCS; 2: PCS+5wt.% nano-Ni; 3: PCS+10wt.% nano-Ni; 4: PCS+5wt.% SiC particle, measured; 2': PCS+5wt.% SiC particle, calculated based on 1; 3': PCS+10wt.% SiC particle, calculated based on 1.

heating rate: 10°C/min; atmosphere: nitrogen.

Fig. 2: IR scheme of the pyrolyzation product of PCS mixed with nano-Co(Ni)

Note: A: PCS+10wt.% nano-Ni; B: PCS+100wt.% PCS. Pyrolyzation temperature: 1: 1000°C; 2: 800°C; 3: 600°C; 4: 400°C. Atmosphere: nitrogen; holding time: 30min.

Heat-treatment of the pyrolyzation production

XRD (RIGAKU 3014) analysis showed that the main component of the pyrolyzation product was metal silicides, and the composition of the pyrolyzation production changed with the heat-treatment temperature (see Table 1). So it is possible to control the electromagnetic property of the modified SiC absorbent by heat-treating it up to different temperature.

Table 1: Composition of chemical plating solution for SiC fiber

	1000°C	1200°C	1400°C	1600°C
5wt.% nano-Co	CoSi, Co ₂ Si, C	—	α-Co, β-Co, C, Co ₂ Si	CoSi, Co ₂ Si, SiC, C
5wt.% nano-Ni	δ-Ni ₂ Si, SiC, C	—	Ni, C, Ni ₅ Si ₂	δ-Ni ₂ Si, Ni ₃ Si ₂ , SiC, C
10wt.% nano-Ni	β-SiC, C, NiO, Ni ₂ Si	β-SiC, C, NiO, Ni ₂ Si	—	—
10wt.% nano-Co	β-SiC, α-SiO ₂ , CoSi	β-SiC, α-SiC, SiO ₂ , CoSi	—	—

From table 1 we also knew that Co(Ni) re-appeared at 1400°C. The reason might be that cobalt (nickel) silicides were reduced by free carbon that was also the product of PCS pyrolyzation. When temperature was elevated to 1600°C, Co (Ni) reacted with SiC and cobalt (nickel) silicides were formed again. This is a reversible reaction:

Control of the electromagnetic parameters of the produced SiC absorbent

Because the permittivity and permeability of the pyrolyzation product could not be measured directly, it was mixed with wax and pressed into wave-guide flange to be a sample. The flange was linked to HP8510C vector network analyzer, and the electromagnetic parameters of the mixture were measured and used to characterize the modified SiC absorbent.

From the discussion in above sections, we know that the modified SiC absorbent is consists of SiC, carbon and silicides. So the electromagnetic property of the absorbent is up to the content and kind of the nano metal powder in the raw mixture. To make the relationship discovered, different content of nano-Co(Ni) powder were homogeneously dispersed into PCS and the mixture was pyrolyzed up to 1000°C in nitrogen. The permittivity and permeability of the product were shown in Fig. 3. As the nano-Co(Ni) content went up, the permittivity of the absorbent increased as we expected, whereas the permeability decreased. This might be due to the oxidation of the metal powder and the silicides formed during pyrolyzation by trace oxygen in nitrogen atmosphere, and Co(Ni) oxides are usually diamagnetic. On the other hand, the permittivity of the pyrolyzation product of PCS mixed with nano-Ni was larger than that of PCS with the same content of nano-Co, because Ni silicides usually have higher conductivity than Co silicides.

Since the composition of the product changes with the pyrolyzation temperature (as discussed above), heat-treatment must be another method to tailoring the electromagnetic property of the modified SiC absorbent. The mixture of PCS and 10wt.% nano-Co was pyrolyzed up to

1000°C and the product was heat-treated in nitrogen at different temperature. Fig. 4 illustrated the influence of heat-treating temperature on μ' and ϵ' of the product. Fig. 4 showed that heat-treatment at lower temperature did not have remarkable effect on the electromagnetic parameters of the product but heat-treatment at higher temperature did. After treated at 1400°C, μ' and ϵ' of the product increased steeply because of the formation of Co(Ni) metal. If the treating temperature was lower than 1400°C, μ' and ϵ' would go down. Although not mentioned in Fig. 4, μ'' and ϵ'' changed with heat-treatment temperature in the same way.

Fig. 3: The permittivity and permeability of the modified SiC absorbent vs the content of nano-Co(Ni) in the raw mixture.

Fig. 4: μ' and ϵ' of the modified SiC absorbent vs heat-treating temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

Addition of nano-Co(Ni) will increase the ceramic yield of PCS, and decrease the content of Si-O-Si bond in the pyrolyzation product. The main component of the product is Co(Ni) silicides that will react with carbon to form Co(Ni) metal when the product is heated to 1400°C. The permeability and permittivity will go up if the content of nano-Co(Ni) in the raw mixture increases, and heat-treatment at high temperature (>1000°C) will increase μ' and ϵ' of the product. Generally speaking, the permittivity and permeability can be altered in a rather wide range: ϵ' : 10-200, ϵ'' : 0-200, μ' : 0-2, μ'' : 0-1.5 (8-12GHz).